

Dengue haemorrhagic fever complicated with hemophagocytic syndrome: A Case report

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ABSTRACT Dengue fever is a common endemic viral illness caused by arbovirus in South Asia including Sri Lanka. The clinical presentation varies from a self-limiting febrile to severe dengue haemorrhagic fever and dengue shock syndrome. Dengue virus-associated hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis is extremely rare, and few cases were reported in the literature. Here, we report a case of Dengue virus-associated hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis in a 32 years old female who presented with an acute febrile illness diagnosed as dengue haemorrhagic fever and subsequently developed hemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis (HLH).

KEYWORDS Dengue haemorrhagic fever, Hemophagocytic syndrome, Pancytopenia, Hyperferritinemia, Hypertriglyceridemia, Corticosteroids

Introduction

Dengue fever is a mosquito-transmitted, arboviral illness, endemic in Sri Lanka, which can present with a wide range of clinical presentations ranging from self-limiting simple dengue fever to life-threatening dengue shock syndrome [1]. Atypical presentation of dengue cases was reported with more severe and fatal outcomes in endemic areas in recent years [1]. Hemophagocytic syndrome is one of rare manifestation of severe dengue haemorrhagic fever and is caused by excessive immune activation which is often misdiagnosed as sepsis and leads to high mortality and morbidity rate among dengue epidemics [2].

Case Report

A 32 years old previously healthy woman was admitted with high-grade, intermittent fever with constitutional symptoms for three days duration. She had no dengue exposure. On examination, she was febrile, flushed with a pulse rate of 116/min, a blood pressure of 100/70 mmHg without a postural drop and a respiratory rate of 28/min. She had a diffuse, blanching erythematous rash over the right arm. Her initial full blood count

Figure 1: The bone marrow biopsy showed hemophagocytic cells.

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Timeline

Figure 2: The timeline illustrates from onset of dengue fever to diagnosis of hemophagocytic syndrome.

showed the evidence of leucopenia with relative lymphocytosis and thrombocytopenia. Dengue NS1 antigen was positive. She was managed according to the national guidelines of dengue fever published by Ministry of Health, Sri Lanka.

On the fifth day of the illness, she developed Malena with a pulse rate of 120/min, blood pressure 90/60mmHg. She had free fluids and pleural effusion detected by ultrasound imaging and low haematocrit, which was required two points blood transfusions. On the 6th day of illness, she developed gum bleeding with severe thrombocytopenia which was required six units of platelets transfusion. Her clinical condition was deteriorated, and she was electively incubated with Glasgow Coma Scale of 7. She had continuous high fever spikes with persistent bicytopenia. Her septic screening was negative. She was managed with empirical broad-spectrum intravenous antibiotics. Her inflammatory markers were high c reactive protein (283mg/L) and normal Erythrocyte sediment rate (35mm/1st hour). Her serum ferritin was 1246 ng/ml. Her clotting profile was high with PT/INR 2.1 of an activated partial thromboplastin time of the 50s. Her fibrinogen level was 3.31 g/L. She had high triglycerides level 843mg/dL. Hemophagocytic syndrome secondary to dengue was confirmed by her bone marrow biopsy showing of pancytopenia and hemophagocytic cells in bone marrow (Figure 1). She was treated with intravenous high dose methylprednisolone for three days and subsequently was managed with oral corticosteroids for two weeks duration. She improved initially with steroid therapy and subsequently was deteriorated and was succumbed at the day of 21. The course of her illness was shown in as Figure 2.

Discussion

Dengue disease is the most prevalent arthropod-borne illness and is transmitted by *Aedes* mosquitoes. Due to the rapidly increasing trend of dengue, it is a considerable health burden causing high morbidity and mortality in endemic countries including Sri Lanka [3].

A major outbreak of dengue was observed in Sri Lanka in 2017 where 185,969 dengue cases have been reported in which 330 deaths occurred with one case of atypical presentation with fatal outcome [3].

Dengue fever is usually self-limiting illness with good recovery. However, it serious complications have been described; among them, the hemophagocytic syndrome also has been reported with fatal outcome in the literature [4]. It has been described commonly in children, with few reports among adults [5]. Diagnosis is a clinical challenge among clinicians, as it can be easily misdiagnosed as sepsis in clinical practice. Therefore, the diagnosis of HLH was confirmed subsequently based on the Histiocyte Society criteria [6] in our patient. HLH is usually associated with DEN1, DEN3 and DEN4 serotypes of dengue viruses [6]. High-grade continuous fever continues with cytopenias and multiorgan dysfunction in dengue fever; clinicians should think the possibility of a diagnosis of HLH. Early recognition and prompt immunosuppressive therapy are beneficial in the morbidity and mortality of such cases [7]. However, she was deteriorated and was succumbed at the day of 21.

It may be possible to treat the triggering condition with corticosteroids therapy and to observe the patient for a response before initiating chemotherapy. It is advisable to avoid chemotherapy among patients with clinical improvement upon treatment of the triggering condition; it may be possible although this is a rare exception rather than the rule. Dexamethasone and etopo-

side are used as induction therapy with intrathecal treatment used for central nervous system involvement [8].

Conclusion

Dengue complicated with the hemophagocytic syndrome is an atypical and rare manifestation in clinical practice. However, Clinicians should be aware of rare manifestation among high-grade continuous fever continues with cytopenias and multiorgan dysfunction in dengue fever. Early recognition and prompt immunosuppressive therapy are beneficial to prevent the morbidity and mortality of such cases because late detection is highly fatal.

Competing Interests

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